

mass without giving the desired product. The synthesis in ethanol medium resulted in a semi-solid mass, which on purification from acetone furnished crystalline products. These compounds are characterised by their physical properties, elemental analysis and oxime and semicarbazone derivative preparation. The anils and their derivatives were analysed satisfactorily for C, H, and N.

The absorption spectra of 3-phenanthryl anils were recorded in ultra-violet region on Beckmann G2400 DU Spectrophotometer in chloroform solution. The first band in the spectra, ranging from 211–284 nm, may be attributed to conjugated azomethine ($>C=N-$) group and second band from 240–297 nm, indicated⁹ the presence of conjugated carbonyl ($>C=O$) group. Another interesting band between 293–321 nm, may be regarded as secondary band of carbonyl group. The higher values may be due to substitution and conjugation in the nucleus. It is also observed that λ_{max} values for azomethine group in ortho substituted compounds is of higher value than those in para and meta-substituted compounds.

The infra-red absorption spectra of these anils were recorded on Infracord spectrophotometer. These spectra showed azomethine ($>C=N-$) absorption band between 1618–1633 cm^{-1} which is considerably lower than that of open chain compounds (1955–1943 cm^{-1}), probably due to conjugation or other side group effects.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected and recorded in an open capillary.

1. Preparation of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal

3-Acetyl phenanthrene¹⁰ (2.0 g) was treated with selenium dioxide (1.5–2.0 g) in 80% acetic acid at 100° and heating continued for 2 hr. The resulting yellow solution had characteristic glyoxalic odour and this on usual treatment, gave yellow amorphous product which was crystallised from acetone in the form of plates, m.p. 104°.

2. Synthesis of Anils

These were synthesised by the usual procedure. One typical example is cited below.

Equimolar quantities of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal and 2-chloro aniline were dissolved in glacial acetic acid and heated at 100° for 2 hr. The resulting solution on decomposition with water gave dark coloured crude product which was crystallised from chloroform (Table 1).

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Optically Active Aliphatic Esters from S-(+)-3-Methylcaproic Acid by Arndt-Eistert Synthesis

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THE preparation and properties of a series of optically active esters of the type (VII) are described (cf. Fig. 1). Compounds (VII) were prepared from the acid chloride (V) through compound (VI) by Arndt-Eistert reaction^{1-3, 4-6}. (V) was prepared by the following known reaction steps: II → III → IV → V.

Figure 1

(I)R' = OH, (II) Br, (III) CH(COOEt)₂, (IV) CH₂COOH, (V) CH₂COCl, (VI) CH₂COCHN₂ (not isolated), (VII) CH₂CH₂COOR.

Experimental

S-(+)-3-Methylcaproic acid (IV)

S-(+)-2-Methyl-1-bromobutane (II)' (116 g) was condensed with sodium salt of ethyl malonate; prepared from sodium (19.8 g), absolute ethanol (350 ml) and diethylmalonate (126 g, 117 ml).

NOTES

Ethyl S-(+)-2-methyl-1-butyl malonate (III), b.p. 195°-200°/15 mm, $\alpha_D^{25} +4.96$, was hydrolysed with a hot solution of potassium hydroxide (47.5 g) in water (47.5 ml) and then decarboxylated by heating with sulphuric acid (44 ml in 110 ml water) for 4 hrs. Residue was extracted with ether and dried with anhydrous magnesium sulphate. After evaporating ether the residual optically active S-(+)-3-methylcaproic acid (IV) was purified by distillation, b.p. 210°; yield 70%.

$$\alpha_D^{25} +4.75; d_4^{25} 0.9679; n_D^{25} 1.433$$

(Found by rapid titration with 0.1*N* sodium hydroxide, M 131.5; C₇H₁₄O₂ requires M 130.0).

mixture was then cooled, filtered, dried and distilled to obtain optically active ester.

Infrared Spectra

Infrared spectra were recorded with a Beckman recording Spectrophotometer (Model IR 5) equipped with a sodium chloride prism, using carbon tetrachloride as solvent.

The physical properties including optical rotation and infrared spectra of the esters are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE I—OPTICALLY ACTIVE ESTERS OF THE TYPE VII

No.	R	Yield %	B.P. °C	Sp. Rotation α_D^{25}	d_4^{25}	n_D^{25}	C=O Stretching vibrations	C—O Stretching vibrations
1.	Methyl	42.0	190-193	+2.76	0.9659	1.413	—	—
2.	Ethyl	44.0	185-187	+2.98	0.9664	1.412	1701 cm ⁻¹ (5.88 μ)	1160 cm ⁻¹ (8.62 μ)
3.	<i>n</i> -Propyl	39.0	198-200	+2.12	0.9672	1.414	—	—
4.	Iso-propyl	40.0	205-207	+1.97	0.9684	1.413	—	—
5.	<i>n</i> -Butyl	52.0	208-210	+3.62	0.9668	1.415	1712 cm ⁻¹ (5.84 μ)	1170 cm ⁻¹ (8.55 μ)
6.	Iso-butyl	48.0	202-204	+2.48	0.9728	1.413	1715 cm ⁻¹ (5.83 μ)	1170 cm ⁻¹ (8.55 μ)
7.	<i>n</i> -Amyl	47.5	220-222	+3.15	0.9787	1.417	1715 cm ⁻¹ (5.83 μ)	1172 cm ⁻¹ (8.53 μ)
8.	<i>n</i> -Hexyl	55.0	170-172	+1.80	0.9872	1.414	1709 cm ⁻¹ (5.85 μ)	1168 cm ⁻¹ (8.56 μ)
9.	<i>n</i> -Heptyl	49.0	205-207	+3.58	0.9881	1.413	—	—
10.	<i>n</i> -Octyl	53.0	230-232	+2.62	0.9883	1.415	—	—

S-(+)-3-Methylcaproyl chloride (V)

S-(+)-3-Methylcaproic acid (130 g, 1.0*M*) was added dropwise during one hour to thionyl chloride (180 g, 1.5*M*) at 10°. It was then refluxed on waterbath for one hour and excess of thionyl chloride was distilled off. The residual acid chloride was purified by distillation at 168°-170°. Yield 57%.

$$\alpha_D^{25} +4.98; d_4^{25} 0.9675; n_D^{25} 1.432$$

General method for the preparation of optically active esters (VII)

S-(+)-3-Methylcaproyl chloride (V) (29.7 g) was added to a solution of diazomethane^{8,9} in ether, prepared from nitrosomethylurea¹⁰⁻¹² (41.2 g) and collected in 500 ml ether. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at 20°-25° for 3 to 4 hrs. The ether was removed under reduced pressure, and to the residual diazoketone, aliphatic alcohol (0.2 mole) and silver oxide (2.0 g) were added. The contents were refluxed for 2 hrs on waterbath. The reaction

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